

Urbanisation and Urban female literacy - A case study of West Bengal

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Abstract: The word urbanization is getting a new dimension in recent years. In the demographic sense urbanization is an increase in the proportion of urban population to total population.

Literacy is a basic indicator of the level of development achieved by a society. Female literacy is considered as a sensitive index of social development compared to overall literacy rates. Female literacy has far reaching consequences on the development of society. Female literacy is negatively related with fertility rates, population growth rates, infant and child mortality and it is positively related with female age to marriage, life expectancy, participation in the modern sectors of the economy.

The objective of this paper is to search a relationship between urbanization and the level of urban female literacy. The paper tries to analyze the relation between urbanization and urban female literacy in India in the post independent period taking into account the census data from 1951 to 2011. For further analysis, census data of urbanization and urban female literacy of states of India are taken into consideration. For disaggregated analysis, data of urbanization and urban female literacy are taken for the districts of West Bengal for the period 1991, 2001 2011.

The proposed work is empirical in nature .Secondary sources of data are used. The Primary census abstract provides data on urban population. Data on literacy are collected from Sarvekshana, India Education Report and Urban West Bengal. The data has been analysed from 1951 to 2011.

For the analysis of data tabular and graphical methods are used. On the other hand descriptive statistics are used for exploratory data analysis.

Keywords: urbanization, literacy, female literacy,urban female literacy

Introduction

In the demographic sense urbanization is an increase in the proportion of urban population to total population.

Literacy is a basic indicator of the level of development achieved by a society. Spread of literacy is associated with modernization, urbanization, industrialization, communication and commerce. Literacy forms an important input in overall development of individuals enabling them to comprehend their social, political and cultural environment better and respond to it appropriately. Higher levels of education and literacy lead to a greater awareness and also contribute in improvement of economic and social conditions. It acts as a catalyst for social upliftment. Literacy rate and educational development affect demographic indicators like, fertility, mortality rates migration etc. It greatly contributes in improving quality of life with regard to life expectancy, infant mortality, learning levels, nutritional levels of children.

Female literacy is considered as a sensitive index of social development compared to overall literacy rates. The Chinese proverb signifies the importance of female literacy. If you plan for a few years, earn money, for ten years, then plant trees, but if you plan for a hundred years, educate the women. According to Mahatma Gandhi, educate one man you educate one person, but educate a woman and you educate a whole civilization. Female literacy has far reaching consequences on the development of society. Female literacy is negatively related with fertility rates, population growth rates, infant and child mortality and it is positively related with female age to marriage, life expectancy, participation in the modern sectors of the economy.

Objective of the paper

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Methodology

The proposed work is empirical in nature .Secondary sources of data are used. The Primary census abstract provides data on urban population. Data on literacy are collected from Sarvekshana, India Education Report and Urban West Bengal. The data has been analysed from 1951 to 2011.

For the analysis of data tabular and graphical methods are used. On the other hand descriptive statistics are used for exploratory data analysis.

Literature Survey

Chandra (2019) examines literacy of Indian women between 1987 and 2017 focusing the gender gap between youths, adults and elderly. She found gender gap has decreased for children and youth but increased for other two classes. Singh (2016) analyses spatial patterns of female literacy and economic development in India. Higher female literacy rate districts are noted for lower proportions of poor populations. Dighe (1996) found benefits from literacy in the form of increased self esteem, autonomy making a study in one resettlement colony of Delhi. Shukla and Misra (2019) evaluated the progress in literacy among the Indian states accounting for age structure in interstate levels. Samudra (2014) examines the trends in female literacy in Maharashtra. Katiyar (2016) analyses gender disparity in literacy across the states and Union territory and indicate future projections of levels of female literacy.

There is an overall paucity of research on women and literacy. The existing studies analysed several aspects of literacy of women. This paper has tried to analyse the relation between urbanization and urban female literacy which has not been found in any previous literature.

Urbanisation, female literacy and urban female literacy of India from 1951 to 2021

Table I: Urbanisation, female literacy rates and urban female literacy rates in the post independent period in India

Census year	Urbanization	Female literacy rates	Urban female literacy rates
1951	17.3	8.66	22.33
1961	18	15.35	40.5
1971	19.9	21.97	48.8
1981	23.34	29.76	56.3
1991	25.71	39.29	64.05
2001	27.8	54.16	73.2
2011	31.16	65.5	79.92
2021	35.4	73.9	82.8

Source: Census of India

Table I shows that level of urbanization has improved in the post independent period from 1951 to 2021 from 17.3 percent to 35.4 percent. In India there has been gradual increase in urbanization since 1951.

Female literacy is an important force multiplier for the social development of a country. Taking into account the female literacy rate and urban female literacy rates in India in the post independent period we find that both the rates have increased over the years. Comparing the female literacy rates and urban female literacy rates it has come out that the rates of urban female literacy are much greater than overall female literacy rates. It clearly indicates that urban females get more educational facility in comparison to rural females. The trend of rising female literates will have far reaching consequences on the development of society.

From the table 1 it comes out that female literacy rates and urban female literacy rates have increased with urbanization from 1951 to 2021. But the rates of increase are poor till 1991. Factors for poor female literacy rates may be: Gender biased inequality, social discrimination and economic exploitation, occupation of girl child in domestic chores, low enrolment of girls in schools and low retention rate and high dropout rate. With the increase in governmental programmes the rates have improved. These are national Literacy Mission, Universalisation of elementary education etc.

Urbanisation and urban female literacy in some selected states of India

Table II: Urbanisation in selected states in India

States	1991	2001	2011
India	25.8	27.8	31.16
Andhra Pradesh	26.89	27.3	33.49
Bihar	13.14	10.46	11.3
Gujarat	34.49	37.36	42.58
Haryana	24.63	28.92	34.79
Karnataka	30.92	33.99	38.57
Kerala	26.39	25.96	47.72
Madhya Pradesh	23.19	26.46	27.63
Maharashtra	38.69	42.43	45.23
Orissa	13.38	14.99	16.68
Punjab	29.55	33.92	37.49
Rajasthan	22.88	23.39	24.89
Tamil Nadu	34.15	44.04	48.45
Uttar Pradesh	19.84	20.78	22.27
West Bengal	27.48	27.97	31.89

Source : Census of India

Considering the data it has been found that urbanization has improved in India.

Table III: Urban female literacy rates in some states of India

States	1991	2001	2011
India	41.17	72.86	79.92
Andhra Pradesh	41.59	68.74	75.02
Bihar	37.19	62.59	72.36
Gujarat	42.05	74.50	82.08
Haryana	40.33	71.34	77.51
Karnataka	42.59	74.12	81.71
Kerala	49.33	90.62	93.33
Madhya Pradesh	39.04	70.47	77.39
Maharashtra	41.48	79.09	85.44
Orissa	39.09	72.87	80.70
Punjab	42.62	74.49	79.62
Rajasthan	35.84	64.67	71.53
Tamil Nadu	43.74	75.99	82.67
Uttar Pradesh	37.83	61.73	71.68
West Bengal	41.54	75.74	81.70

Source: Census of India

Considering the literacy rates of urban women in the states of India in 1991, 2001 and 2011 we find that the first position was occupied by the state Kerala in all the three years. In 1991, the second position is occupied by Tamil Nadu and Punjab is in third position. In 2001 and 2011 the second position is occupied by Maharashtra and the third position went to Tamil Nadu. These are the states where levels of urbanization have been found to be relatively high in comparison to other states. The states with low levels of urbanization have been found to have low level of urban female literacy. These states are Rajasthan, Bihar, Orissa and Uttar Pradesh. Among these four states Bihar, Rajasthan Uttar Pradesh along with Madhya Pradesh have been considered as BIMARU states. These are the problem states of India in terms of a number of socio economic indicators. In all these states feudal values of the past continue to exist in different forms. Social, cultural and historical factors inhibited the improvement of literacy level of women in these states.

But there are some states like Madhya Pradesh and Andhra Pradesh where the levels of urbanisation are quite impressive but that have not helped in improving the literacy rate of urban women. It shows that apart from the infrastructural facility, there are some factors like attitude towards women which also matters in the case of level of women literacy. But the situation has changed. Over the last decade a remarkable shift in the approach to female education has been that education for women is being considered as a basic human right and a crucial input for national development. The National Policy of education (NPE) 1986 and its programme of action give education a mandate to work for women's equality and empowerment.

Table IV: Literacy rates among urban females across MPCE Group and states (1900-2000)

MPCE/state	350-425	425-500	500-575	575-665	665-775	775-915	915-1120	1120-1500	1500-1925	1925+	ALL
Andhra Pradesh	466	567	599	665	708	764	820	882	922	974	666
Assam	653	723	813	832	879	926	910	917	977	953	808
Bihar	455	586	593	703	828	862	870	926	970	994	595
Gujarat	494	617	657	736	719	834	878	898	948	967	766
Haryana	444	384	565	686	717	726	730	827	896	905	675
Karnataka	608	629	696	711	749	775	867	893	964	946	757
Kerala	869	861	892	886	916	932	922	958	957	954	912
Madhya Pradesh	537	569	673	723	779	800	830	870	934	971	676
Maharashtra	653	690	709	730	798	799	853	890	956	970	792
Orissa	493	615	706	703	815	868	890	931	983	992	662
Punjab	558	616	614	687	708	769	815	869	923	941	734
Rajasthan	394	474	531	587	658	692	814	841	898	916	625
Tamilnadu	662	693	694	774	782	786	867	904	956	943	785
Uttar Pradesh	468	499	613	658	745	716	784	880	909	927	614
West Bengal	559	627	666	774	831	854	924	927	968	956	763
All India	541	603	653	713	768	789	843	892	942	956	723

Source : Census of India

Variations in overall urban female literacy rates are much wider, varying from 60 percent in Bihar to 91 percent in Kerala. Kerala, Maharashtra, Gujarat, Assam, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal are among the states with high urban female literacy rates. Assam is not

among the most prosperous states, but has a particularly high rank, only next to Kerala in female literacy. Income levels and poverty appear to be important factors in literacy, but this relationship is truer within the states than across states. From the table it comes out that the urban female literacy rate rises consistently with the rising monthly per capita expenditure class (MPCE), for each of the states without exception. At the household level, literacy is a function of income levels, and this relationship is statistically significant.

At lower levels of income, the performance of the states in urban female literacy varies much more widely. Performance is more or less the same at higher levels of income. Thus it comes out that there are strong external factors which determine the household's performance in literacy. These external factors would be socio cultural environment in the state, government expenditure on primary education and literacy and measures taken for assuring good quality of schooling, etc. It has also been found that these factors mostly affect the poor. A relatively poorer state could achieve better results by creating a more favourable external environment. The literacy level of Punjab is lower than Orissa. Punjab ranks very high in per capita state domestic product while Orissa is almost at the bottom. But performance of Orissa in literacy is higher than that of Punjab. Kerala achieved high levels of literacy when income levels were low in the state. The governmental efforts play an important part in literacy attainments. It appears paradoxical that external factors affect mostly the poor people but poor have little influence on these factors.

Urbanisation and Urban female literacy in Districts of West Bengal

Table V: Level of urbanization in districts of West Bengal

Districts	1991	2001	2011
Darjiling	30.71	32.34	38.99
Jalpaiguri	16.40	17.84	27
KochBihar	7.85	9.1	10.25
Uttar Dinajpur	13.33	12.06	12.07
Dakshin Dinajpur		13.1	14.13
Maldah	7.08	7.32	13.8
Murshidabad	10.41	12.49	19.79
Birbhum	8.98	8.57	12.8
Bardhaman	35.43	36.94	39.87
Nadia	22.65	21.27	27.81
North 24 Paraganas	50.83	54.3	57.03
Hughli	30.94	33.47	38.62
Bankura	8.31	7.37	8.36
Purulia	9.48	10.07	12.75
Haora	49.54	50.36	63.3
Kolkata	100	100	100
South 24 Parganas	12.49	15.73	25.61
Pashchim Medinipur	10	11.9	12.03
Purba Medinipur		8.29	11.65
West Bengal	27.48	27.97	31.89

Source : Urban West Bengal

It can be seen that level of urbanization has improved in the districts of West Bengal in the years 1991, 2001 and in 2011.

Table VI: Rates of Urban female literacy in districts of West Bengal

Districts	1991	2001	2011
Darjiling	71	78.52	83.65
Jalpaiguri	63	74.07	77.78
KochBihar	72	79.77	85.54
Uttar Dinajpur	70	74.84	76.69
Dakshin Dinajpur		78.55	86.14
Maldah	66	73.85	74.71
Murshidabad	52	60.75	68.02
Birbhum	58	70.20	76.55
Bardhaman	62	69.29	76.63
Nadia	66	75.70	81.98
North 24 Paraganas	72	80.37	86.66
Hughli	70	77.46	83.95
Bankura	63	71.91	79.24
Purulia	58	64.91	67.21
Haora	66	75.78	79.09
Kolkata	72	77.30	82.25
South 24 Parganas	64	73.70	84.52
Pashchim Medinipur	70	75.73	84.98

Purba Medinipur		76.33	82.3
West Bengal	68	75.74	80.98

Source : Urban west Bengal

Taking into account the urban female literacy in the districts of West Bengal it has been found that Kolkata being one of the biggest metropolitan cities of the country obviously occupied the first position in this regard.

In all the three years, Higher rates of urban female literacy are found in Howrah, Hughli ,North 24 Paraganas. These are the districts where level of urbanization had been found to be high. Whereas Murshidabad, Birbhum and Purulia are found to have both lower rates of urbanization as well as urban female literacy rates. Darjiling is found to have medium level of Urbanisation because of its hill areas but urban female literacy is quite high in Darjiling. Maldah, Koch Bihar and South 24 Paraganas have low levels of urbanization but high levels of urban female literacy rates.

The southern districts near to metropolitan Kolkata exhibits higher rate of literacy on the other hand the districts of North Bengal and Western plateau region have lower literacy rate due to historical background of backwardness. It is believed that some socioeconomic factors influence the literacy rate considerably. Therefore the positive relation between urbanization and level of urban female literacy although cannot be generalized in all cases but can be found in many cases.

In 1991, the level of urban female literacy has improved remarkably for the state of West Bengal with many other states of India. This is probably because of the World bank aided District Primary Education Programme (DPEP) launched in the mid 1990s.This programme specifically focuses on districts with female literacy below the national average.

To encourage the education of women at all levels and sending them to schools Government of West Bengal is providing many concessions by providing free books, uniform, bicycles, midday meals ,scholarships and so on. Kanyasree project is highly successful in reducing drop out of female students from the schools.

A Correlation Analysis:

The simplest method to examine the presence of any relationship between two variables is to estimate the correlation coefficient between the two variables. This method has its limitations- notably it assumes that the relationship is linear . However it remains the simplest , easiest and commonly used method.

The Pearson correlation has been estimated . The results are presented in Table VII

Table VII:Regression coefficients of levels of urbanization and urban female literacy rates of some selected states of India

Year	Number of observations	R square
1991	13	0.28
2001	13	0.23
2011	13	0.57

Source : Author Calculation

The regression results showing the correlation between level of urbanization and level of urban female literacy of some selected states of India have been found to be positive in the years 1991,2001and 2011. Increasing urbanization provides not only more civic amenities but also relatively more infrastructural facilities for women in terms of more schools colleges. But except in 2011, the values are not very high.

But there are some states like Madhya Pradesh and Andhra Pradesh where the levels of urbanisation are quite impressive but that have not helped in improving the literacy rate of urban women. It shows that apart from the infrastructural facility, there are some factors like attitude towards women which also matters in the case of level of women literacy. But the situation has changed. Over the last decade a remarkable shift in the approach to female education has been that education for women is being considered as a basic human right and a crucial input for national development.The National Policy of education (NPE) 1986 ant its programme of action give education a mandate to work for womens equality and empowerment.

Table VIII:Regression coefficients of levels of urbanization and urban female literacy rates of districts of West Bengal

Year	Number of observations	R square
1991	18	0.18
2001	18	0.094
2011	18	0.045

Source : Author Calculation

Conclusion:

In the case of West Bengal the correlation between urbanization and urban female literay has been found to be positive but the low values of correlation coefficients indicate that the relation between the two are not very strong. Whereas urbanization is an economic part of development, literacy has socio economic perspectives. Mere economic development may not bring about a drastic improvement of literacy especially female literacy. For improvement of female literacy rates a social reform is needed where a female child will be considered not as a burden but a productive factor of development.

Bibliography:

- Chandra Tanusree,(2019) Literacy in India: The Gender and Age Dimension,ORF Issue Brief No. 322, observer Research Foundation
- Dighe Anita, (1996) The Impact of Literacy on Women in India, Unesco Institute of Education
Directorate of Census operation, Census of India
Institute of Local Government and Urban Studies , Urban West Bengal
- Katiyar Shiv Prakash, (2016) Gender Disparity in Literature in India, Sage Publication , Vol 46 Issue 1
- Samudra Aparna, (2014) Trends and Factors Affecting Female Literacy- An Interdistrict Study of Maharastra, International Journal of Gender and Womens' Studies, American Research Institute for Policy Development
- Shukla Vachaspati& Mishra S Udaya, (2019) Literacy Achievement in India, Vol 54, Issue No. 48 Economic and Political Weekly
- Singh Ripudaman, (2016) Female Literacy and Economic Development in India, Rupkatha journal, DOI: 10.21659/rupkatha.v8n2.07

